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ADPI
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MUNDARIJA

PEDAGOGIKA

Yulbarsova X.A. Bo'lajak sotsiologlarda ijtimoiy kompetentlikni rivojlantirish tuzilmasi va tavsifi	4
Xushnazarova M.N. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni ijtimoiy pedagogik amaliyotga tayyorlashda pedagogika fanining samarali usullaridan foydalanish	10
Raxmedova M.A. Mahmud az-Zamaxshariyning ma'naviy merosidan yoshlarni axloqiy tarbiyalashda foydalanish imkoniyatlari	13
Ismoilov Y.Q. Bo'lajak jismoniy madaniyat o'qituvchilarini ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalashning texnologik masalalari	17
Iminova H.M. Ta'lim tizimiga konsentrlangan ta'limni integratsiya qilishning zamonaviy pedagogik tendensiyalari	20
Muladjanova G.A., Mullajonova M.D. Oliy ta'lim talabalarining sun'iy intellekt tizimlaridan foydalanish kompetentligini takomillashtirish	25
Wang Ping. Exploration of ethnic music elements in chinese piano works	29
Kadirov A.M., Ergasheva Sh.Q. The role of fine arts in installing the values of human dignity in general education pupils	32
Nadirxanova N.A. Enhancing creative competence in students through the steam educational methodology: integrating visual arts and engineering graphics	38
Axmedova D.X. Interfaol usulda rag'batlantirishning o'quvchilar ta'lim-tarbiyasiga ijobiy ta'siri	44
O'rinboyev M. I. Fizika o'qitish amaliyotida metakognitiv faoliyatlarni takomillashtirish	48
Burxonova M.M., Sirojiddinov B.A. Amaliy mashq va masalalarning kontekstual asoslari hamda umumta'lim maktablarda qo'llanilishi bo'yicha pedagogik-metodik aspektlar	51
To'raxonova B.T. Bo'lajak pedagog-psixologlarni tarbiyaviy faoliyatini tashkil etishga tayyorlashning pedagogik imkoniyatlari	54
O'smanova D.Z. Zamonaviy dars jarayonida adabiy-nutqiy kompetensiyani shakllantirish, ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalar orqali rivojlantirish	57
Xudoyberganova M.A. Talabalarga adabiyotni o'qitishda ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan foydalanishning samarali texnologiyalari	61
Iminova D.N. Innovativ loyihalar vositasida boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarida o'qish motivatsiyasini rivojlantirishning mazmuni	65
Abdulmadjidova M.D. Ilk o'spirinlik davrida mehnatga munosabatning shakllanishi	68
Dushabayeva G.M. Mustaqil ta'limda chizmachilik fanidan kompyuter dasturlarda foydalanishning ahamiyati	71
Utanova V.M. Diskurs tahlili: umumiy ta'rif, metodologiya va misol	75
Qoraboyev J.B., Qoraboyeva N.N. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida frazeologik ma'no tuzilishi	78
Umarov A.V. Ilmiy-ma'rifiy media loyihalar – talabalarining mediasavodxonligi va axborot madaniyatini rivojlantiruvchi didaktik vosita sifatida	81
Qodirova O.S. Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshida bolalarning ta'lim faoliyatiga faol tashabbuskorlik munosabatini shakllantirishning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari	86
Aslonov X.Sh. Dasturlangan laboratoriya ishlarida yarimo'tkazgichlarning ta'qiqlangan zona kengligi tushunchasi	89
Bakirov I.H. Boks sport turida musobaqalarning o'tkazish turlari va musobaqa faoliyati	94
Saidg'aniyev S.O. Bolalar uchun sport gimnastikasi	98
Tojiboyeva N.T. Ta'lim muhitida o'zini-o'zi boshqarishda qiyin bo'lgan o'smirlarning hissiy qulayligining psixologik jihatlari	100
Dushabayev D.Sh. Umum ta'lim maktablarda jismoniy tarbiya darslarida zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish	103
Abdullaev G'A. The method of determination of aerobic and anaerobic treshhold by heart rate of athletes in the development of endurance qualities in athletics training (In the case of middle and long distance runners)	106
Qurbonova F.M. Talabalarining jamoada ishlash qobiliyatlarini kollobratsiya asosida shakllantirishning psixologik xususiyatlari	110
Shobduraximova U.T. Tavakallchilikka asoslangan virtual o'yinlar va ularning jamiyatga salbiy ta'siri	113
Hasanova S.K. Development of creative thinking of primary class students based on pirls' flows	115
No'monova A.N. O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimiga tasviriy san'atning rang tasvir yo'nalishini tadqiq etishning dolzarb masalalari	119
Toshtemirov Q.Q. Umumiy o'rta ta'lim maktablari musiqa madaniyati darslarida milliy musiqa merosi "shashmaqom"ni o'rganishning ahamiyati	122
Gofurjanova N.K. Boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilarini xalqaro baholash dasturlaridagi ishtirokning ta'lim sifatini oshirishdagi o'rni	126
IJTIMOIY GUMANITAR FANLAR	
Yusupova S.N., Bakhronov B. Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning dolzarb muamolari	129
Olimova Z.I. Abdulla Avloniyning Turkiston o'lkasidagi jadidchilik harakatiga qo'shgan hissasi	132
Mirzayeva B. Maishiy zo'ravonlikning ijtimoiy-falsafiy mohiyati	134

O'quvchilarda jismoniy tarbiya fanini o'qishda zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalar orqali nazariy va amaliy bilimlarni oshirish muhim ilmiy, pedagogik muammo hisoblanadi [6]. Buning uchun, yangi o'qitish metodlari, jumladan zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalardan foydalanish zarur bo'ladi.

Shunday qilib, jismoniy tarbiya o'qituvchisini yangi talablar sharoitida o'quv jarayonini loyihalash nafaqat ta'lim natijalarini rejalashtirishga, balki ta'lim mazmuni, usullari, shakllari va texnologiyalarini tanlashga boshqa yondashuvlarni ham nazarda tutadi. Jismoniy tarbiyada zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalardan foydalanish, eng avvalo, jismoniy tarbiya va sportga qiziqishni oshirish maqsadida pedagogik jarayonga ijodiy yondashishdir. Bu salomatlikni saqlash uchun o'quv jarayoni darajasini oshirish vazifasi bilan bog'liq va bizning asosiy maqsadimizdir.

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THE METHOD OF DETERMINATION OF AEROBIC AND ANAEROBIC TRESHHOLD BY HEART RATE OF ATHLETES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENDURANCE QUALITIES IN ATHLETICS TRAINING (IN THE CASE OF MIDDLE AND LONG DISTANCE RUNNERS)

<https://zenodo.org/records/13292483>

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Abstract. *In this article, we explore the individualized approach to developing endurance qualities in long-distance athletics. By analyzing athletes' specific test results through Anaerobic Threshold (AT) and Heart Rate Reserve (HRR), we can identify athletes' aerobic and anaerobic zones. These specific test results are designed to efficiently organize athletes' training processes. The scientific method plays a crucial role in enhancing athletes' endurance qualities.*

Key words: *endurance, aerobic, anaerobic, physical qualities, speed, recovery, HRR (heart rate reserve), specific practical test.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье мы рассматриваем метод индивидуального подхода к спортсменам в развитии качеств выносливости в легкоатлетической тренировке. При развитии выносливости мы определяем аэробную и анаэробную зоны спортсменов по результатам специальных практических испытаний через Ан.МЧ (анаэробный метаболический предел) и ЮУЧ (частота пульса). Результаты этого специального практического теста ориентированы на эффективную организацию тренировочного процесса. Этот научный метод имеет большое значение в развитии выносливости спортсменов.*

Ключевые слова: *выносливость, аэробность, анаэробность, физические качества, скорость, утомляемость, частота сердечных сокращений, специальный практический тест.*

Аннотация. *Ushbu maqolada biz yengil atletika mashg'ulotlarida chidamlilik fazilatlarini rivojlantirishda sportchilarga individual yondoshish usulini ko'rib chiqildi. Chidamlilikni rivojlantirishda*

biz An.MCH (anaerob metabolik chegara) va YUUCH (yurak urish tezligi) orqali maxsus amaliy sinovlar natijalariga ko'ra sportchilarning aerob va anaerob zonalarini aniqlandi. Ushbu maxsus amaliy test natijalari o'quv jarayonini samarali tashkil etishga qaratilgan. Ushbu ilmiy usul sportchilarning chidamliligini rivojlantirishda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: chidamlilik, aeroblik, anaeroblik, jismoniy fazilatlar, tezlik, charchoq, yurak urishi, maxsus amaliyot testi.

Endurance is considered one of the fundamental factors in developing physical qualities in all structural components of physical fitness. Engaging in activities that do not develop endurance without improving endurance qualities makes it quite complex to repeat other types of activities in sufficient volume. When developing endurance qualities, we distribute the workload to athletes based on their individual characteristics, taking into account the athlete's physiological capabilities. Using this method, athletes carry out activities in a clearly defined direction during the training process and perform activities based on scientific principles.

Today, numerous scientific and pedagogical works are being conducted and research is ongoing regarding the types of long-distance athletics and the development of endurance qualities in athletes. In foreign countries, several scientific and practical works have been carried out to improve the endurance qualities of long-distance runners [1]. American specialists Rob Sleamaker and Ray Browning have conducted scientific research on endurance, which is still being applied by athletes and their coaches today. Finnish physiologist Martti Karvonen (1918-2009) developed a formula to determine anaerobic and aerobic thresholds based on heart rate frequency, which is currently used to distribute training loads for athletes. In 1982, Italian Olympic sports physician Francesco Conconi collaborated with sports doctors to conduct significant research on determining the lactate threshold of athletes through heart rate frequency. Nurullaev Abduhamid Rozyimboevich, an associate professor at Bukhara State University, emphasized the importance of foreign experiences in developing physical endurance qualities in students in his article "Foreign Experiences in Developing Physical Endurance Qualities in Students". The lack of scientific studies and research conducted on individualized endurance qualities of athletes who engage in medium and long-distance running in our country was highlighted during the analysis of scientific literature [2].

As a result, it was determined that research results have not been obtained as a scientific object for studying the physical fitness levels of athletes who engage in medium and long-distance running in individualized training conditions. Consequently, the necessity of developing scientific-based training programs and optimal variants of physical exercises for these athletes based on the results obtained through determining their physical fitness levels became apparent.

The study pointed out the importance of analyzing and optimizing training programs and exercise regimes for medium and long-distance runners based on their physical fitness levels, particularly those running distances of 3000m and 5000m. By identifying and specifying physical loads based on their capabilities, it was suggested that enhancing athletes' professional skills could be achieved.

This manual is considered essential for implementing physical education classes, engaging in athletics sports, post-class sports activities, and daily physical health improvement activities for athletes involved in these sports disciplines [3].

The article describes the development of athletes' endurance qualities in long and medium-distance running disciplines by determining aerobic and anaerobic zones through

heart rate frequency during sports such as track and field athletics. It discusses the methods used by developed countries to enhance endurance in athletes.

Endurance is a crucial aspect of physical qualities in every sports discipline. Endurance refers to a sportsperson's ability to sustain high-intensity processes over a long period of time, and the duration of this endurance determines the athlete's endurance qualities. "Tolikish" or fatigue occurs when this endurance is prolonged over a long period. High-level athletes possess unique characteristics in their endurance qualities. Athletes continue training in a fatigued state without reaching high intensity to develop their skills and abilities [4]. These factors are taken into account to enhance athletes' endurance qualities, using various methods and introducing new techniques. Proper distribution of loads during physical activities makes it easier for athletes to achieve high results.

There are two main types of endurance training:

- Aerobic Endurance
- Anaerobic Endurance

Aerobic endurance refers to the ability of muscles to perform work and movements using energy produced with the help of oxygen. Aerobic endurance can be developed through continuous or interval training. The longer the duration of the event, the more important aerobic endurance becomes.

Anaerobic endurance, on the other hand, refers to the ability of muscles to work without the presence of oxygen, using energy systems that do not require oxygen. When developing endurance qualities, it is important to organize training loads based on the athlete's physiological capabilities. How can we determine the Anaerobic Threshold (An.AT) without going to the laboratory? Let's take a look at these in this article [5].

The transition from aerobic to anaerobic energy supply system due to an increase in lactate accumulation rate with a rapid increase in exercise intensity is called the Anaerobic Threshold (AT). The increase in exercise intensity with an increase in lactate accumulation rate is crucial for athletes who need to perform at moderate and long distances [6]. Therefore, if your training program is chosen correctly, then the increase in lactate accumulation rate should lead to an increase in speed and approach to maximal heart rate.[6] Understanding lactate threshold is a critical factor for athletes striving to improve their performance. As a result, workouts should be conducted at both high-intensity levels and at a slightly slower pace (recovery workouts). Creating individual intensity zones based on lactate threshold or heart rate knowledge is essential for athletes to optimize their training [7].

The method of determining the boundaries of Aerobic and Anaerobic through heart rate frequency (HRF) allows athletes to accurately perform their training loads based on the correct regimen [8]. To implement this method, a treadmill, stopwatch, and a helper who records heart rate results are needed.

Athletes perform a specific practical test in the following order:

1. The athlete warms up by jogging 4 km (warm-up) and performs stretching exercises before starting the Special Practical Test (SPT). It is crucial for the athlete to be well warmed up before taking the test [9].

2. After completing the stretching exercises, the athlete starts the main part of the SPT. This involves running a continuous 6-minute run. The time between each lap is indicated as 1 letter. For example, if the athlete completes the first lap in 4 minutes and 40 seconds, they start the second lap after a break of 1 minute and 20 seconds. The speed of the laps increases, and the recovery time decreases as the test progresses [10].

3. After running each 1000 meters, the athlete's heart rate is measured and recorded every 6 seconds. The athlete gradually increases their speed during the test. Any deviations of 2-3

seconds in the running time shown in Graph 1 do not affect the results of the Special Practical Test.

4. The results of the Special Practical Test are plotted on a graph comparing heart rate to running times. The graph shows the relationship between Heart Rate (HR) and Running Times for the athlete. We record HR results on the Y-axis and plot the athlete's running times on the X-axis (as shown in Graph 1) [11].

During the process of conducting a specific practical test for athletes, the stage-by-stage increase in speed is observed, leading to an increase in Heart Rate (HR), and ultimately, the athlete's Anaerobic Threshold (An.MCH) is determined. In other words, during the final stage of the special test trials, when the athlete reaches their maximum effort, the Anaerobic Threshold is crossed. At this crossing point (cruising speed), the athlete's speed at that moment is calculated based on their physiological capabilities on that day. The primary goal of these special test trials is to determine the athlete's maximum speed. It involves identifying the point where the Aerobic and Anaerobic zones intersect. (The point where the athlete crosses is indicated by letter "a" in Table 2). Therefore, if we analyze the physiological capabilities of the athlete on that particular day, the result at the point where Aerobic and Anaerobic zones intersect was determined to be 3 minutes and 20 seconds.

Table – 1

№	The athlete's performance according to the training schedule.	The athlete's HRM-result.	Recovery time between repeated sprints.
1	4 min.40. сек.	110 у/м	1min.20 сек. recovery
2	4min.30. сек.	120 у/м	1min.20 сек. recovery
3	4min.20. сек.	130 у/м	1min.40. сек. recovery
4	4min.00. сек.	150 у/м	2 min. recovery
5	3min.40.сек.	160 у/м	2 min.20 сек. recovery
6	3.05. МИН (runners should run with the maximum effort in the last attempt).	200 у/м	-

Table - 2

Developing endurance in sports requires a unique set of skills and individualized training methods. The correct approach to training plays a crucial role in improving endurance in athletics. Using the right methodological approach helps athletes achieve high results in competitions. By determining the athlete's Anaerobic Threshold (An.MCH) through Heart Rate (HR) monitoring, we can easily organize training sessions with precise measurements and goals. This approach enables athletes to perform workouts without overexertion. Choosing the right methodological approach to improving endurance helps athletes excel in sports competitions.

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TALABALARINING JAMOADA ISHLASH QOBILYATLARINI KOLLOBRATSIYA ASOSIDA SHAKLLANTIRISHNING PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI

<https://zenodo.org/records/13292503>

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Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolada oliy ta'lim muassasalarida ijtimoiy rivojlanishni takomillashtirish va ta'lim sohasidagi munosabatlar va ishtirokchilar o'rtasidagi kollobratsiya (hamkorlik) amaliyotning ilmiy va amaliy tadqiqotlariga bag'ishlangan. Shuningdek, talabalarda jamoaviy rivojlanishda kollobratsion yondashuvning o'rni va ahamiyati hamda hamkorlik asosida faoliyat olib borishidagi pedagogik- psixologik xususiyatlar haqida so'z yuritiladi. Shu bilan bir qattorda talabalarida hamkorlik yondashuv vositasida pedagogik ijtimoiylashuvini rivojlantirish usullari haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *hamkorlik, psixologik xususiyat, hamkor tashkilot, professional kompetensiya, jamoaviy rivojlanish, qonunchilik ta'lim dasturlari, uzluksiz ta'lim.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена научно-практическим исследованиям вопросов совершенствования профессионального развития в высших учебных заведениях и практики сотрудничества (сотрудничества) между отношениями и участниками сферы образования. Обсуждаются роль и значение кооперативного подхода в профессиональном становлении студентов, педагогико-психологические особенности работы на основе кооперации. Была представлена информация о методах развития педагогической профессиональной подготовки студентов на основе сотрудничества.*

Ключевые слова: *развитие сотрудничества, психологические характеристики, партнерские организации, профессиональные компетенции, личностно-профессиональное развитие, педагогическая концепция сотрудничества, юридические образовательные программы, непрерывное образование.*

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the scientific and practical studies of the improvement of professional development in higher educational institutions and the cooperation (cooperation) practice*

